

Fintech Integrated Cooperative Banking System in India: “Mission Sahkar se Vitteey Praudyogikeekaran”

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Abstract

Financial technology (Fintech) has emerged as an innovative force in the global financial ecosystem. Fintech has transformed banking and financial service delivery by leveraging digital innovation. In India, Cooperative societies operate at the grassroots level, contributing significantly to economic development. In India, there are more than ~1 lakh PACS/MPACS, 32 State Cooperative Banks, 338 District Central Cooperative Banks (DCCBs) and ~1,457 urban Cooperative Banks that contribute heavily to economic growth. The cooperative sector, which includes Cooperative banks and credit societies, is critical to achieving financial inclusion, rural development, and economic empowerment at the grassroots level. However, outdated operating models with manual processes, limited technology, technological infrastructure, and low digital reach have hampered their efficiency and competitiveness. The adoption of FinTech by cooperative banks and credit societies creates significant opportunities for modernizing these institutions while also boosting their reach, transparency, and sustainability. That is, FinTech and Cooperation will integrate to increase financial and technological inclusion in India, while also boosting economic growth, which contributes to long-term development and realising the vision Viksit Bharat@2047. In this paper, an attempt has been made to frame the fundamental components of the FinTech integrated Cooperative Banking System in India. Research paper also underlines the key linkages between FinTech integrated Credit Cooperatives and Financial Inclusion, with focusing on Autonomation, Efficiency, Accessibility, and Innovation. Furthermore, the study highlights the crucial part of PACS/MPACS in providing eServices in rural India, which leads to inclusive growth, considering the mission “Sahkar se eSuvidha”. The Paper also covers the various initiatives for the Digitalization's of Cooperatives, which promotes Financial inclusive which, focusing on the major goal of cooperative identity “Sahkar se Samriddhi”.

Keywords

Financial technology (FinTech), Cooperative Credit Societies, Cooperative Bank, eServices, Ministry of Cooperation.

Introduction

The world of today is dependent on technology, and humans are surrounded by it. One of the most important aspects of the above is FinTech, often known as Financial Technology. FinTech has caused dramatic changes in the global financial sector. FinTech involves digital technologies that provide financial services in a streamlined and secure manner, including mobile banking, online lending, digital payments, blockchain and security, and Artificial intelligence (AI). These innovative service offerings have upset the traditional banking model by increasing accessibility, lowering operational costs, and improving the customer experience. In India, The Government initiatives such as Digital India, Jan Dhan Yojana, Aadhar, and Unified Payments Interface (UPI), which encourage the development of digital infrastructure, have expedited the adoption of FinTech in financial services. In this ever-changing world, cooperative banks and credit societies hold a unique position. The cooperative movement in India has long been an important instrument for rural credit, agricultural support, and socioeconomic development. Cooperatives are founded on the concepts of mutual help, democratic governance, and community participation. Primary Agricultural Credit Societies (PACS), District Central Cooperative Banks (DCCBs), State Cooperative Banks (SCBs), and Urban Cooperative Banks (UCBs) comprise a vast network that primarily serves farmers, small business owners, and the economically weaker sections. Primary Agricultural Credit Societies (PACS) are increasingly acting as Common Service Centres (CECs), providing critical digital and financial services in rural communities. They serve as local access points for banking, insurance, e-governance, and welfare programs, thereby increasing last-mile connection and financial inclusion. By using their grassroots presence and member trust, PACS improves service delivery, transparency, and rural socioeconomic development. Despite their broad reach, cooperatives have always relied on manual record-keeping, paper-based transactions, and local operations. Such techniques have frequently resulted in inefficiencies, delays, limited

transparency, and significant operational hazards. Furthermore, competition from commercial banks, microfinance institutions, and digital payment platforms has increased the demand for modernization. FinTech presents interesting options to overcome these systemic flaws. Core Banking Solutions (CBS), mobile and internet banking, digital wallets, Aadhaar-enabled payment systems, automated loan processing, and data analytics for credit evaluation are among the FinTech innovations integrated into cooperative banking operations. For remote residents, digital services minimize travel time and transaction costs, encouraging financial inclusion

Objective of study

The main objective of the research study is to frame the fundamental components of the FinTech integrated Cooperative Banking System in India. It also underlines the key linkages between FinTech integrated Credit Cooperatives and Financial Inclusion, with focusing on Autonomation, Efficiency, Accessibility, and Innovation. It also covers the various initiatives for the Digitalization's of Cooperatives which promotes Financial inclusive which focusing the major goal of cooperative identity "Sahkar se Samridhhi". It highlights a crucial part of PACS/MPACS in providing eServices in rural India, which leads to inclusive growth, considering the mission "Sahkar se eSuvidha".

Review of Literature

Sugiyanto, S., & Setiawan, W.L. (2022) studied that the integration of fintech in credit cooperatives improves efficiency and financial performance. A case study of an Indonesian rural cooperative highlighted that there is an increase in active membership, credit transactions, and savings mobilization, as well as a decrease in non-performing loans and operating costs after the adoption of fintech. Furthermore, concluded that fintech can make cooperative finance simultaneously meet financial and social goals, and fintech-based cooperative models can serve as an inclusive financial infrastructure that bridges the gap between the formal banking system and marginalized communities. **Kaurav, P. (2025)** investigated how innovation promotes sustainability and competitiveness in cooperatives. The study used a thematic analysis approach, which allows for the discovery of common themes in sustainability initiatives, technological adoption, financial models, and policy interventions. And also highlighted that long-term performance depends on embracing innovation, financial technology, and current management techniques. Furthermore, it is recommended that digital transformation, blockchain, AI-driven solutions, and mobile banking be combined to increase operational efficiency, financial inclusion, and governance. **Mahale, P., & Mithunraj, B. (2025)** explored the national cooperation policy's rationale, components, and projected outcomes. The findings suggested that the strategy is more than just a change of cooperative administration; it is also a strategic realignment of cooperatives as digital economic entities. Furthermore, also highlighted that Cooperatives focused on specific sectors are more relevant to the economic realities of the twenty-first century. The paper suggested concrete approaches such as professional training programs, digital literacy initiatives, cooperative branding, and the establishment of a cooperative innovation fund. **Singh, D., & Bairathi, V. (2025)** examined the influence of significant government initiatives such as cooperative credit reforms, subsidies, digitalization efforts, and the recent establishment of a dedicated Ministry of Cooperation on cooperatives' growth and sustainability in India. Furthermore, the study demonstrated how government support has improved credit access, operational efficiency, member participation, and grassroots socioeconomic development. **Hardiyanto, F., & Hidayat, A. R. (2025)** explored the role of blockchain technology in increasing transparency and accountability in cooperatives that save and borrow in Indonesia and the theoretical understanding of blockchain applications in financial management for cooperatives, as well as practical insights for managers and policymakers. Furthermore, the paper also underlined the need for technology education for cooperative members in order to enable effective blockchain adoption and advised broadening the analysis of blockchain's long-term implications and applications in diverse cooperative sectors in Indonesia.

Methodology

The research paper is an attempt at exploratory research, based on secondary data. The required secondary data for completing the investigation will be collected mainly from published sources in Journals, Articles, Web, Government reports, the National Cooperative Database, etc. An attempt has been made to understand the various initiatives for the Digitalization's of Cooperatives, which promotes Financial inclusive which, focusing on the major goal of cooperative identity "Sahkar se Samridhhi".

Analysis

7.0 Concept of Fintech Integrated Credit Cooperatives:

Source: Developed from Review of literature

Fintech refers to offering rapid and easy financial services via the use of modern technologies. Integrating Fintech into cooperative banks and credit societies improves the efficiency of digital banking services. Mobile banking, and UPI enable members to transact from home. The Core Banking System (CBS) integrates all branches into a single network. Digital loan processing speeds up and transparently processes loan approvals. Aadhaar-based e-KYC and online documents save time and money. Blockchain technology makes transactions safe, unchangeable, and reliable, reducing fraud. Fintech enhances financial inclusion, allowing people in rural areas to access banking services. Data analytics improves risk management and credit assessment accuracy. Cybersecurity systems safeguard members' money and information. Government regulation promotes compliance, consumer protection, and financial stability. Innovation creates digital payments, AI-powered credit assessments, and Fintech applications. Fintech integration helps cooperatives become more modern, transparent, and competitive.

8.0 Various Government Initiatives for FinTech & Digitalization of Cooperatives:

8.1 Sahakar Digi Pay & Sahakar Digi Loan Apps Digi Pay and Sahakar Digi Loan Apps are digital financial applications designed for cooperative banks and credit societies to provide members with convenient and fast banking services. Digi Pay allows clients to transfer money, pay bills, check balances, and make digital payments via UPI directly from their mobile device. Sahakar Digi Loan App allows for online loan applications, document uploads, and a quick approval process. These apps eliminate paperwork, saving both time and money. As a result, cooperative transparency grows, and financial inclusion in rural communities improves. (www.timesofindia.com)

8.2 Computerization of Primary Agricultural Credit Societies The Government of India, under the Ministry of Cooperation have launched the Computerization Scheme for Primary Agricultural Credit Societies (PACS), which would connect them to a standard ERP-based platform, allowing all PACS to work digitally. This system allows PACS to complete tasks such as loan processing, financial transactions, and accounting in a timely and transparent manner. Computerization speeds up loan disbursement, lowers expenses, and allows PACS to better link with state and national banks. It also allows for the tracking and management of PACS data online, as well as improved farmer support services. The primary goal of this program is to transform PACS into a contemporary, efficient, and dependable financial service center. (www.cooperation.gov.in)

8.3 Simplified Aadhaar System for Cooperative Banks The Simplified Aadhaar System is a new digital framework created in conjunction with UIDAI (Unique Identification Authority of India) and the cooperative sector, allowing cooperative banks to quickly implement Aadhaar-based authentication and e-KYC services. Under the new system, state cooperative banks would be directly registered with UIDAI, and district central banks would be able to conduct Aadhaar-based transactions using their state banks' technical and IT infrastructure, lowering costs and technical complexity. The reforms include biometric e-KYC, face authentication, Aadhaar Payment Bridge, and Aadhaar Enabled Payment System (AePS), which are significant steps toward the government's financial inclusion and digital banking goals. This technique makes it easier to open bank accounts and get direct pay or subsidies, particularly in rural and semi-urban areas. Cooperative banks are using this program to provide their members with fast, safe, and easy digital

services. (www.cooperativebanks.in)**8.4 PACS to function as Common Service Centres (CSC)** Primary Agricultural Credit Societies (PACS) will now operate as Common Service Centres (CSCs) under the Government of India plan, providing over 300 digital and societal services to rural communities. MoUs have been signed with the Ministries (Cooperation, Electronics, and IT) and NABARD about PACS, allowing banking, insurance, Aadhaar enrolment/updates, legal assistance, and other services to be made available via PACS. This effort will broaden the scope of PACS by making them economically self-sufficient and multi-service hubs. Farmers and rural inhabitants will benefit the most from these services, as they will now be able to access various government and corporate services at the local level. In this way, PACS will promote both digital and financial inclusiveness. (www.business-standard.com)**8.5 National Cooperation Policy 2025** The primary goal of the National Cooperation Policy 2025 is to make the cooperative sector more professional, transparent, and technologically advanced, allowing PACS, credit cooperative banks, and other cooperative institutions to utilize digital technology. The policy provides recommendations on making common banking software, digital payments, and IT-based services available in order to increase digitalization and technology use, resulting in faster and safer service delivery for clients. This strategy also includes guidelines on how to reinforce vital digital infrastructure and cybersecurity by encouraging the use of technology in cooperative credit and banking departments. Work in this regard will boost financial inclusion in rural areas and service coverage, particularly in PACS and District Central Cooperative Banks. (www.cooperation.gov.in)**9.0 Figure No. 01 An Integrated framework for FinTech Integrated Cooperative Banking System Focusing on Vitteey Praudyogikeekaran:**

Source: Developed from Review of literature

An Integrated framework for FinTech Integrated Cooperative Banking System Focusing on Vitteey Praudyogikeekaran given in Figure No. 01. Cooperative Banks and Rural Credit Cooperatives in India are increasingly incorporating financial technology (FinTech) to modernize service delivery, improve transparency, and strengthen last-mile financial inclusion through a coordinated ecosystem led by the Ministry of Cooperation in collaboration with the National Payments Corporation of India, the Indian Banks' Association, and the Reserve Bank of India. This "whole-of-government" strategy seeks to develop a unified, technology-enabled cooperative banking system that connects Primary Agricultural Credit Societies (PACS), District Central Cooperative Banks, and State Cooperative Banks via a seamless digital network. Within this framework, technologies like Sahakar Digi pay promote interoperable digital payments, allowing Cooperative Banks to provide UPI-based transactions, Aadhaar-enabled payments, micro-ATM services, and direct benefit transfers to rural members. By digitizing payment flows, these organizations minimize cash reliance, improve transaction traceability, and speed up settlement, therefore strengthening governance and member confidence. In addition, Sahakar Digi Loan offers an app-based credit delivery system that speeds up loan origination, paperwork, KYC verification, credit score, and payout. The digital loan module reduces paperwork, shortens turnaround times, and broadens access to timely and inexpensive financing for members, self-help organizations, and small businesses, ultimately boosting rural livelihoods and agricultural output. Sahakar Sarathi Private Limited frequently serves as an implementation and service partner for cooperative institutions, including core banking integration, cybersecurity, cloud hosting, analytics,

and capacity-building solutions. Together, these approaches enable data-driven decision-making, consistent regulatory compliance, and increased operational efficiency throughout the cooperative credit framework. Collaboration with national payment systems and regulatory agencies guarantees compatibility with traditional banking channels, allowing cooperative banks to compete with commercial banks while maintaining their member-centric focus. Fintech-integrated cooperative banking systems promote autonomy, efficiency, accessibility, and innovation, which leads to Sahkar se Vitteey Praudyogikeekaran (financial inclusion) all of which align with India's overarching digital transformation goals and rural development priorities. **10.0 Figure No. 02 Road Map for Promoting eServices through PACS/MPACS in India: "Sahkar se eSuvidha":**

Source: Develop from Review of literature

Road Map for Promoting eServices through PACS/MPACS in India given in Figure No. 02. The integration of Primary Agricultural Credit Societies (PACS) into the Common Service Centre (CSC) program represents a watershed moment in India's cooperative movement. Historically, PACS served largely as short-term finance organizations for farmers. However, the innovative "Sahkar-se-Samriddhi" (Prosperity via Cooperation) program involves collaboration between the Ministry of Cooperation, the Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology, NABARD, and CSC. PACS will serve as CSCs, thereby transforming them into multi-service centers at the grassroots. This transformation allows PACS to provide e-services to rural communities, such as banking, insurance, Aadhaar enrolment, PAN card services, and numerous government-to-citizen (G2C) initiatives like Ayushman Bharat and PM-Kisan, which promote Sahkar se eSuvidha. The framework aims to close the digital gap in distant locations where commercial service providers are typically absent. This not only improves rural people's digital literacy, but it also ensures that farmers have access to important services right at their doorstep. Economically, this approach tackles the long-standing question of PACS's financial viability. PACS as CSCs indicate a strategic progression in the cooperative sector. It enables local communities by offering a "one-step solution" for digital and financial requirements, boosting the rural economy and promoting a more inclusive digital India.

Conclusion

The cooperative banking system plays an important part in the economic growth of the common people. The incorporation of FinTech into the cooperative banking system is not only necessary, but also critical to its survival and expansion. These institutions can improve financial inclusion by connecting conventional banking practices with technological solutions. The adoption of FinTech in the cooperative banking system improves efficiency, lowers operating costs, and allows depositors and members to get faster and more transparent services. However, during this shift, cybersecurity and data privacy concerns must be addressed. If the cooperative sector adapts to FinTech, it can thrive in a competitive market and play a more important role in economic growth for the average person. By integrating cooperative principles with FinTech, this technique strengthens grassroots financial institutions. It presents them as vital drivers of inclusive growth, resilient rural finance, and long-term socioeconomic development across the nation, which leads to "Sahkar se Samriddhi".

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